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Assessment of Psychological Approach in Managing Industrial Disputes at University System of Education among Parents in Ilorin Metropolis, Kwara State

Ajayi, Beatrice Tayo

Department of Educational Psychology and Counselling,
Adeyemi Federal University of Education, Ondo, Ondo State, Nigeria

Email: drtayocyajayi@yahoo.com

Tel: +234 8035727363

Abstract

This study investigated parents' opinion on the relevance and evident application of psychological concepts and principles in managing industrial disputes at Nigerian university system of education by the Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU) and the Federal government. This study adopts the descriptive survey research design. All working-class parents in Ilorin metropolis of Kwara State having children as undergraduates at Nigerian public universities during the 2021/2022 academic session form the population for the study. Sample consists of 400 parents (206 male and 194 female) undergraduate sandwich students of Kwara State College of Education, Ilorin selected using purposive random sampling technique. Respondents were workers at federal, state, and privately-owned establishments in Ilorin metropolis, Kwara State. One research question and three null hypotheses guided this study. The Psychological Approach in Managing Industrial Disputes at University System of Education (PAMIDUSEQ) developed by the researcher was used for data collection. The validity of the instrument was ascertained by two specialists in the field of educational psychology and measurement and evaluation respectively, of educational psychology and Counselling department, Adeyemi Federal University of Education, Ondo. The reliability coefficient of 0.78 obtained through test-retest exercise determined the reliability of the instrument. Research question was answered using descriptive statistic of mean score while the t-test and ANNOVA statistics were used for data analysis at 0.05 level of significance. Result among others revealed parents' expressed relevance of psychological concepts and principles in managing industrial disputes at university system of education though its application by ASUU and federal government was not obvious. The study recommends need for university management, ASUU and federal government to incorporate psychological concepts involving positive incentives and actions of responsiveness having potential to address fundamental needs and fears of ASUU rather than threat or victimization approach.

Keywords: Psychological Approach, Industrial Dispute, Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU), Federal Government

Introduction

Industrial dispute has come to be regarded as one of the most visible perennial problems of significance in Nigerian university campuses. The educational system in Nigeria has witnessed an unprecedented industrial unrest and official assaults than other social institutions over the last thirty years (Adesulu, 2013). Nationwide strike actions frequently embarked upon by the Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU) are unduly prolonged with the end of a dispute catalysing onset of another. The depressive consequences of the incessant and intractable industrial dispute have been profoundly felt on homes, schools, and organisations. The typically prolonged ASSU strikes are not only demanding but stressful, painful, exhausting, and costly in human terms and on the quality of Nigerian graduates due to time loss. Its psychological effect on the part of students who must stay idle at home, lamenting their woes and causing irritation to parents cannot be overemphasised (Osagiobare et al., 2019). Consequently, the strategic position of university in the nation's hierarchy of priorities, its roles as veritable machine for development, knowledge and value provider, brain box of a country, the fountain for intellectualism and the most appropriate ground for incubation of tomorrow leaders appear being obviously challenged.

Conflict stems from pluralism and respect for diversity and is psychologically and socially healthy in providing conditions for social changes and democracy (Kelman, 2008). Different from the general conception, conflict is also inevitable as human relationship issues are at its root (Kelman, 2008 & ghaffar, 2008). When a group is faced with non-fulfillment of basic physiological needs including physical safety, physical wellbeing, identity, recognition, autonomy, self-esteem, and sense of justice however, conflict is likely inevitable. Conflict, though considered as normal, anticipated, and a reflection of staff and employers' incompatibility of interests, goals or values with each other (Johansen, 2012 & Henry, 2009) can be required to defy people to perform and stimulate progress (Hotepo et al., 2010) and to attain optimum organizational effectiveness (Obi et

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al., 2015), can be unhealthy. Additionally, unresolved conflict can be highly demanding, stressful, exhausting, and costly both in human and material terms but if managed effectively, can facilitate progress and development among groups.

Industrial dispute ensues as a disagreement among people, institutions, groups, communities and nations, through which the parties involved perceive threat to their needs, interest or concerns (Ghaffar, 2008; Hotepo et al, 2010; Johansen 2012), when they perceive that they are getting less than their fair share or that equity has not prevailed on issues that affect their interest and that participating parties in industrial relations are unable to reach peaceful agreements as it affects job rules and conditions of job generally (Henry 2009). The Nigerian labour market has witnessed several unresolved industrial conflicts designated as inevitable, normal, anticipated and not necessarily dysfunction but suggestive of strained industrial relations between the academic staff and the Federal Government of Nigeria.

The incessant industrial disputes in Nigerian university system dates to over thirty years and has continue to be a factor in academic life to the extent that predictive phenomenon has it that students would spend some months at home for a given academic session. The wastage of years meant for investment into academic activities is a huge setback rendering impossible timely course completion. Going by record of ASUU strike in year duration, Universities were closed for; 2 months in 1981 2months in 1988, 3 months in 1992 and 4months in 1993 (Osagiobare et al.,2019) Universities were closed 6 months in 1996, 3 months in1999, 6 months in 2001and 6 months in 2003(Uzor et al., 2020). Universities were also closed for 4 months in 2008, 5 months in 2009, 1 month in 2011, 5 months in 2013, 35 days in 2017, 95 days in 2018 and 9 months in 2020 (Uzor et al., 2020). Cumulatively, students at Nigerian Universities have spent over 2 years observing different strike actions. The huge wastage of years meant for investment into academic activities at universities is obviously doing the country's education no good and requires effective conflict management approach that limits the negative effects of conflict while increasing its positive aspects and improve group outcome or performance (Dontigney, 2018).

This study proposes relevance of psychological concepts and principles in managing industrial disputes at Nigerian university system of education to facilitate progress and development among groups. As postulated by Kelman (2008), painfully and frustratingly perceived rights' denial is a stimulus which ordinarily breeds discontent with unmet expectation. It consequently gives room for frustration, discontent, uprising and protest (Aluede et al., (2004). The theory of relative deprivation to social psychologists therefore is a gap between what people get (value capability, such as social status, welfare) and what they perceive they should (value expectations). This theory explains that once people's standard of living has started to improve, their level of expectation rises. If improvement in actual conditions drops, the urge to revolt emerges (Aluede et al., 2004). Denied human expectations, interests, needs, concerns, aspirations, and positions can be so intensely felt that it can degenerate with little catalysis into frustration, mass demonstration, violence and political instability. The theory of relative deprivation thus seems to account for welfare problems which also explain the causality of industrial dispute in the Nigerian university system. ASUU strikes are triggered partly by perceived deprivation of needs, rights, interests, and concern that borders on their work and welfare (Henry, 2009 & Dontigney, 2018). Some suggested psychological concepts and principles considered effective in managing industrial disputes are stated below:

Collaborating is one of the underlying principles that underscore successful conflict resolutions (Uzor et al.,2020). It fundamentally involves teamwork and cooperation in helping everyone or both parties achieve their goals while also maintaining relationships. It is a win- win resolution as each party is involved in search for the best solution to the conflict in a constructive manner considering the needs, desires, feelings and expressing the concern of each party. Its process of working through differences will lead to creative solutions that will satisfy both parties' concerns. It is used when there is a high level of trust and when you want others to have ownership of solutions. It is also used when the people involved are willing to change their thinking as more information is found and new options are suggested (Dontigney, 2018).

Accommodating strategy essentially entails giving the opposite side what it wants (Dontigney, 2018). I lose, you win approach fundamentally involves working towards a common purpose as more important than any other concerns, it occurs when one of the parties wishes to keep the peace or perceives the issue as minor. It helps to appease others by downplaying conflict, thus protecting relationships. This approach is used when an issue is less important to one party than it is to the other. It is used when you realise the wrong when you know you cannot win and when harmony is extremely important (Dontigney, 2018).

Compromising: This approach of 'I bend you bend' is on the fundamental premise of winning something while losing a little bit. The strategic philosophy is to place both ends against the middle in attempting to serve the "common good" while ensuring each team can maintain each of their original position. There is concern for outcome as well as relationship. Both parties try to reach an agreement that will give both some of what they want that will have no side effect on their relationship (Dontigney, 2018).

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Forcing is a win –lose resolution. The concern for the outcome here is high and requires the use of authority by the forcing individual. The use of the strategy is firm, not willing to give ground, intent of pursuing his goals. When both parties use this strategy, considerable hostility is likely because each is trying to gain the upper hand. This approach builds up resentment and hostility. Only one group will be happy about it (Dontigney, 2018).

Avoiding strategy seeks to put off conflict indefinitely by delaying or ignoring the conflict, the avoider hopes the problem resolves itself without a confrontation. In some cases, avoiding can serve as a profitable conflict management strategy such as the dismissal of a popular but unproductive employee. The hiring of a more productive replacement for the position soothes much of the conflict. However, those who actively avoid conflict frequently have low esteem or hold apposition of low power (Dontigney, 2018).

Psychological attitude of human respect according to Kelman, (2008) is the first approach for treating human relation issue. The principle of intergroup cooperation explains that animosity between groups subside when they engage in a joint activity to achieve mutually shared goals. Psychological principles and concepts of inter-group cooperation, persuasion, and mutual respect to achieve mutually shared goals is of high relevance for identifying real problems and addressing them. Solutions will only be found when the real problem is addressed (Shamir,2013). However, peoples’ personal perceptions, past experiences and expectations manifested in rational or irrational decisions influence the outcome of such negotiations at negotiation tables. The mediation process for instance involves interaction of various kinds during which emotion can affect the judgment of the parties like strong feeling resulting in irrational decisions that are counterproductive and even harmful to the parties (Shamir, 2013). This probably might have formed the bedrock of failed past negotiations for which strike actions had been recurrent at Nigerian universities.

Industrial disputes at Nigerian University system of education remain incessant and persistent over decades despite its numerous negative outcomes of distorted academic calendar, heavy losses of resources and even human life. The difficulty of stake holders of university education to deal promptly with industrial dispute, stem it down and prevent its escalation suggests that effective management of industrial disputes in Nigerian system remains a tussle. Unduly prolonged strike actions in the Nigerian university system not only threatens the ideals of the institution but pose great challenges to its strategic positions in the nation’s hierarchy of priorities and roles as a veritable machine for development, fountain of intellectualism, knowledge, value provider and the most appropriate ground for the incubation of leaders of tomorrow (Akinwale et al., 2023).

The sources of discontent for ASUU crisis in Nigerian University system are in exhaustive. They point to the unresolved deep –seated problems that underlie the ASUU-Federal Government conflict, the authoritarian attitudes of the government and university management towards labour issues, corruption in all segments of the society and maladministration (Solaja,2015). Other problems include mismanagement of public utilities and fund, unmotivated workforce, poor policy execution, underfunding of social services which to ASUU have led to a combination of decline in facilities, dilapidation of existing but often outdated infrastructure as well as fundamental decay in the university system (Solaja, 2015 & Akinwale, 2023). The signs of collapse began to show in the 1980’s and became evident in the 1990’s in the form of acute shortage of research and learning facilities (buildings, technology tools, laboratories, science, and engineering equipments, lecture theaters, digital libraries, constant electricity supply) for both staff and students (Enakoko,2013). Some engineering workshops operate under zinc sheds and trees. Due to lack of reagents and tools to conduct experiments, many science-based facilities are running what is referred to as ‘Dry Lab’ (Adesulu, 2013). Whereas ASUU regards the economy of the country as quite buoyant to provide required facilities for universities, past governments’ preference to spend money on frivolous things and use cosmetic solutions to handle strike actions is perceived to account for the present deterioration state. The failure of the Federal government to implement duly signed agreement by the government and ASUU since 1992 is claimed by ASUU as a basis for intensive context of repeated national strike.

Parents and students who are often worse hit by effects of strike actions are often persistent in their call to both the federal government and ASUU for prompt resolution of disputes rather than engaging the use of irrelevant and ineffective accusations that are incapable of removing outstanding barriers that have been hindering favourable resolution of disputes over years. While the union insist that the Federal government must honour the 2009 agreement by providing the funds according to the timetable and conditions both parties set (Enakoko,2013), Nigerians also clamour for use of more relevant protest approach order than strike actions now less popular as it once seemed in the 20th century by ASUU (Adesulu , 2013).

Human relationships are found at the root of disputes. Therefore, imperative, and helpful is the application of psychological concepts and principles that foster favourable relationships and removal of barriers to manage of industrial dispute in the university system. Previous research on industrial disputes have focused on nature and causes of conflict in schools (Ghaffar,2008) and causes of industrial disputes in Nigerian university system as well (Hotepo et al., 2010). Studies

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are however rare in the literature on the psychological approach in managing industrial dispute at the Nigerian university system. This is the gap which the present study seeks to fill.

Objectives of the Study

The objective of this study was to:

1. Assess the relevance of psychological approach in managing industrial disputes at the Nigerian university system of education.
2. Determine the respondents' opinion on application of psychological approach in managing industrial disputes at the Nigerian university system of education by university management, ASUU, and the federal government.

Research Question

The following research question was answered in this study:

1. Do parents' mean score response indicate the relevance of psychological approach in managing industrial disputes at Nigerian university system of education?

Hypotheses

1. Parents do not differ significantly in their opinion on application of psychological approach in managing industrial disputes at university system of education by university management based on the number of their children affected by the strike.
2. There is no significant gender difference in parents' opinion on application of psychological approach by ASUU in managing industrial disputes at the Nigerian university system of education.
3. There is no significant difference in parents' opinion on application of psychological approach in managing industrial disputes at Nigerian university system of education based on marital status type.

Methodology

Descriptive survey was adopted for this study. The population of this study consists of all working-class parents in Ilorin metropolis, Kwara State who have children studying in Nigerian public universities at the time of conducting the study. Sample size consists of 400 (206 (51.5%) male and 194 (48.5%) female) working class parents in Ilorin metropolis, Kwara State, Nigeria. Their marital status reveals 218 (54.5%) parents living with spouses, 148 (37.0%) single parents and 34 (8.5%) widowed. Parents with a single child affected in the unrest are 281 (70.3%) and those having two children and above affected in the unrest, 119(29.8%). Parents type of occupation reveals that 289(72.3%) are civil servants and 111(27.8%), privately employed. Type of children's university proprietorship reveals 176(44.0%) federal government, 132 (33.0%) state and 92 (23.0%) private type.

The researchers' designed instrument titled "Psychological Approach in Managing Industrial Disputes at University System of Education Questionnaire" (PAMIDUSEQ) was used for data collection. Construction of items of the instrument was based on the reviewed literature, media information and personal experience on patterns employed for handling ASUU strike by ASUU and the federal government of Nigeria. The instruments' section A of the four-point modified Renis Likert Type 18 items questionnaire solicited for information on biodata of respondents, while section B contained items on psychological approaches for managing industrial disputes in Nigerian universities. The instrument's items were scored weighing from four (4) for Strongly Agree (SA) to 1 for strongly Disagree (SD). In decision making, an item was considered positive if the mean score reaches 2.5 and above. The (PAMIDUSEQ) was face and content validated by two experts in Educational Psychology and Counseling department, Adeyemi Federal University of Education, Ondo, Ondo State, Nigeria.

Administration of the instrument was personally conducted by the study researchers with the help of two trained research assistants on randomly selected respondents at workplaces. A total of 430 copies of the instrument were administered after which the completed copies of the instrument were collected within one hour. Out of the four hundred and thirty copies of the questionnaire administered, 400 adequately completed ones were used for analysis in this study.

Results

Research Question 1

Do parents' mean score response indicate the relevance of psychological approach in managing industrial disputes at Nigerian university system of education?

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Table 1: Mean score on the relevance of psychological approach in managing industrial disputes at Nigerian university system of education.

.S/N	ITEMS	N	Mean	SD	Decision
1	PREVENTING: Taking time to obtain information that can lead to dispute and using it to change decisions that forestall strike action.	400	3.33	.884	Accepted
2	Developing dispute prevention measures and best solutions in constructive manner considering groups' needs, interest and feelings	400	3.39	.748	Accepted
3	Accepting to work through differences with high level of trust to find a win-win-solution to the problem	400	3.4	.716	Accepted
4	COLLABORATING: Using mediation approach that establishes a cooperative problem-solving result	400	3.40	.788	Accepted
5	COLLABORATING: Putting in place teamwork, mediation approaches that address the fundamental fears of the other party	400	3.29	.773	Accepted
6	COLLABORATING: Directing negotiation towards conflict resolution that will satisfy the concern of both parties.	400	3.36	.794	Accepted
7	FORCING: Displaying firm resistance and lack of willingness by forcing authority to give ground for the other group	400	2.12	.77	Rejected
8	FORCING: Pursuing own group's viewpoint at the expense of another group	400	2.04	.76	Rejected
9	FORCING: Pursuing one's party's goals to gain upper hand despite resistance from the other group	400	1.26	.73	Rejected
10	COMPROMISING: Working on each party's problems to the extent that both give up something of lesser importance	400	3.28	.89	Rejected
11	COMPROMISING: Engaging in dialogue in meaningful ways until both parties have attained mutually satisfactory solutions that will give some of what they want.	400	3.28	.87	Rejected
12	COMPROMISING: Focusing on expectant and mutually acceptable solutions to each other's' problems	400	3.21	.96	Accepted
13	ACCOMODATING: Employing responsiveness to the other party's concerns and needs rather than prioritizing one's party's goals.	400	3.11	.92	Accepted
14	ACCOMODATING: Creating a favorable environment for negotiating.	400	3.44	.74	Accepted
15	ACCOMODATING: Creating a trust environment that offers other party's earlier agreed promises	400	3.30	.84	Accepted
16	ACCOMODATING: Making available confidence building measures	400	3.29	.86	Accepted
17	AVOIDING: Ignoring dispute rather than address the fundamental fears of the other party	400	1.27	.78	Rejected
18	AVOIDING Delaying response to dispute rather than settlement hoping the problem resolves itself.	400	2.20	.795	Rejected

Source: Field survey, 2022

Table 1 reveals eighteen listed conflict resolution measures to which respondents were to indicate the degree of relevance of each to managing industrial disputes in Nigerian universities. Results reveal parent's expressed relevance of psychological approach to management of industrial disputes in Nigeria universities except for the measure of forcing and avoiding as indicated in low mean scores below 2.5. The most accepted as relevant measures of high mean scores above 2.5 being: creating a favorable environment for negotiating and implementing such agreement, next is finding out the history of the conflict and the other identifying attempts already made to solve the problem.

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Hypothesis 1:

Parents do not differ significantly in their opinion on application of psychological approach in managing industrial disputes at university system of education by university management based on the number of their children affected by the strike.

Table 2: T-test analysis of difference in parents’ opinion on evident use of psychological approach in managing industrial disputes at Nigerian universities system of education by university management based on the number of children affected.

Children Affected by industrial action	N	X	SD	DF	t.cal.	t.val.	decision
One Child	281	59.32	5.62	398	-.752	1.97	NS
Two Children and above	119	59.76	5.00				

Source: Field survey, 2022

Results on table 2 reveals t calculated value $-.756$, degree of freedom 398 at .05 level of significance. Since the calculated value $-.756$ is less than the critical table value 1.97, the research hypothesis is accepted, which means there is no significant difference in the opinion of parents on the relevance of psychological approach for handling industrial dispute by university management in Nigerian universities based on the number of children affected by the strike.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant gender difference in parents’ opinion on application of psychological approach by ASUU in managing industrial disputes at the university system of education.

Table 3: T-test analysis on application of psychological approach in managing industrial disputes at Nigerian university system of education based on gender

Gender	N	X	SD	DF	t.cal.	t.val.	Decision
Male	206	59.50	5.74	398	-.226	1.97	N.S
Female	196	59.39	5.12				

Source: Field survey,2022.

Result on the table 3 reveals t calculated value, $-.226$, degree of freedom 398 at .05 level of significance. Since the calculated t-value $-.226$ is less than the critical table value 1.97, the null hypothesis was accepted, which means, there is no significant difference in the opinion of male and female parents on evident use of psychological approach for managing industrial disputes in Nigerian universities by ASUU, the labor union.

Hypothesis 3:

There is no significant difference in parents’ opinion on application of psychological approach in managing industrial disputes at Nigerian university system of education based on marital status type.

Table 4: Analysis of variance on parents’ opinion on application of psychological approach in managing industrial disputes at Nigerian university system of education by the federal government based on marital status type.

Source of Variance	SS	DF	MS	Cal.F ratio	Critical F ratio.	Decision
Between Groups	47.229	2	23.614	.797	3.00	A
Within Groups	11767.771	397	29.642			
Total	118115.000	399				

Source: Field survey,2022.

Table 4 indicates the one-way Analysis of variance (ANNOVA) value of $.797$, DF 399 with $P=.452$. Since the calculated F-ratio is lower than critical F ratio 3.00 at .05 level significance, the hypothesis was accepted. This means that there is no significant difference in the opinion of parents on the relevance of psychological approach for managing industrial disputes in Nigerian universities by the federal government, based on type of marital status.

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Discussion of Findings

Responses to the only research question of this study reveal the relevance of psychological approaches of preventing, collaborating, compromising, and accommodating to industrial disputes management in the university system but that forcing and avoiding approaches are not. Findings agree with earlier researchers of Johansen (2012) that conflict management behaviours are partially situated and that the approach for managing conflict is chosen to match the situation at hand. Result is therefore in line with researchers' advocacy for shift in labour's use of strike actions for managing industrial dispute and federal government use of more effective approach of collaboration to curb outbreak and resolve industrial disputes in an efficient manner that could result in improved quality staff morale (Ajayi, 2020 & Johansen, 2012).

Result also reveals no significant difference in parents' opinion on evident application of psychological approach for management of industrial dispute by universities management based on the number of their children that are affected by industrial disputes. The finding agrees with that of Iredia (2013) that most people, including parents wish that university managers could reduce frustrations in their campuses by identifying with the needs of both staff and students, rather than threat. Also related is Iredia's (2013) finding that industrial disputes in Nigerian universities, being the result of administrators' inability to recognise conflict, view conflicts' constructive as well as destructive potential, learn how to manage conflict and apply conflict management strategies in practical way. Enakoko (2013) therefore advocated a more judicious use of internally generated revenue collected yearly by university managers for possible positive impacts on the overcrowded facilities in Nigerian universities hence its tendency to prevent strike outbreak. It is glaring therefore that irrespective of the number of children of a parent affected by industrial dispute parents feel grossed alike being those that mostly bear the brunt of industrial disputes as their children sit idle at home, with tendency of them getting involved in anti-social vices.

Result reveals no significant difference in the opinion of male and female parents on evident use of psychological approach for handling industrial dispute in Nigerian universities by ASUU. This result agrees with Adesulu (2013) findings on parent's opinion of absence of definite actions to end strikes in Nigerian universities by ASSU and Federal government with students at the receiving end. The result however disagrees with that of Adesulu (2013) that strike, the means of protest by ASUU is no longer popular as it once seemed in the 20th century and calls for review.

Result also reveals no significant difference in respondents' opinion on evident use of psychological approach for handling industrial disputes in Nigerian universities based on type of marital status. The result agrees with that of Adesulu (2013) and Hetepo et al (2010) that the inability of Nigerian universities to successfully attain and achieve the set goals and objectives is the result of poorly managed industrial disputes by the federal government. Result also agrees with that of Enakoko (2013) and (Akinwale et al., 2023) that fertile ground for onset and escalation of strike actions is provided by governments' avoidance and non-responsiveness to financial needs and desire of Nigerian universities.

Conclusion

Educators are quick to advocate replacement of a seemingly ineffective method of industrial dispute for a more effective one. The view very much lends credence to the passionate appeal for university management, labour union and federal government for shift in their regular strike approaches to manage industrial dispute to enable smooth running of school calendar, incentives, and more positive results order than mere promises. Relevance of psychological approach to industrial dispute management in Nigerian universities is established by respondents of this study, its use however for positive results was not evidently ascertained.

Recommendations

1. University management, labour union and the federal government should endeavor to employ psychological strategies of preventing, accommodating, collaborating and compromising that involve positive incentives and actions of responsiveness in addressing fundamentals needs and fears of the other party through positive steps and not threats,
2. University management, labour union and the federal government need to engage in dialogues that address conflict management behaviour as a first step in creating a healthy work environment. The prevalent use of avoidance of avoidance by university management as conflict management strategy prevents proper address of the root of problems.
3. Arrangement ought to be in place for educating and training of university staff, their management and undergraduate business programmes in conflict management strategies. This can go a long way to prevent, address and effectively resolve conflict. Providing more conflict management training in an undergraduate business programme could help raise the

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emotional intelligence of future managers so they are more likely able to use problem-solving skills instead of trying to bargain.

4. Because conflicts are part of human interactions and nature, university management, ASSU and federal government should employ psychological approach to resolve and manage industrial disputes as they arise before escalating to unmanageable level.

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